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Educational Policies Implementation As Predictor Of Teachers' Productivity In Public Junior Secondary Schools In Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study examined educational policies implementation as predictor of teachers' productivity in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. The study was guided by three objectives, three research questions and three null hypotheses. The study adopted a correlation survey research design, with a population of 7,492 teachers from 354 public junior secondary schools in Rivers State. The sample size of the study was 749 teachers representing 10% of the entire population which was drawn from the population using stratified sampling technique. The instrument was a questionnaire of two sets titled: Educational Policies Implementation Questionnaire (EPIQ) and Teachers' Productivity Questionnaire (TPQ). The instrument was validated and the reliability was tested using Cronbach alpha method, which yielded reliability coefficients of 0.81 and 0.87 for EPIQ and TPQ. For method of data analysis, the research questions were answered using simple regression, while the hypotheses were tested with t-test associated with simple regression at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that physical facilities policy implementation significantly predict teachers' productivity in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State, while teachers' development and student-teacher policies implementation do not significantly predict teachers' productivity. Based on this finding, it was recommended among others that government should implement teacher development policy by sponsoring teachers for conferences and workshops to enhance their pedagogical skills for improved productivity. Also, government should recruit more junior secondary teachers in order to get it right with students-teacher ratio policy so as to improve teachers' productivity.

Keywords: Educational Policies, Implementation, Teachers' Productivity

INTRODUCTION

Globally, it has been acknowledged that education is a key to speedy socioeconomic growth and development of any country. This implies that any society that intends to progress particularly in this hi-tech era needs good educational system that will equip her citizens for the ever-changing and advancing world. Nigeria like other nations in the world has reached a stage in development when it must tackle the problem of defining its educational goals in terms of concepts, need and overhauling. This is what necessitates a structure or framework that will look at the successes and failures of past educational system with a view of determining its impact on teacher productivity.

Every human endeavor has laws, rules or stipulations that serve as an over-all guide on what activities should be carried out and how those activities are to be carried out so as to achieve set objectives. These laws, rules or stipulations are succinctly referred to as policy.

A policy defines the area in which decisions are to be made, but it does not make the decision. It usually provides a backing that facilitates decision-making. In the same vein, educational policies provide the basis or direction for educational activities in the bid to achieve the stupendous goals of education (Okoroma, 2017). Education policy consists of the principles and government policies in the educational sphere as well as the collection of laws and rules that govern the operation of education systems. Education occurs in many forms for many purposes through many institutions. Examples include early childhood education, kindergarten through to 12th grade, two and four year colleges or universities, graduate and professional education, adult education and job training (Ekpoh, et al., 2023). Therefore, education policy can directly affect the education people engage in at all ages. Examples of areas subject to debate in education policy, specifically from the field of schools, include school size, class size, school choice, school privatization, tracking, teacher selection, education and certification, teacher pay, teaching methods, curricular content, graduation requirements, school infrastructure investment, and the values that schools are expected to uphold and model.

Issues in education policy also address problems within higher education. Sadly, educational policies had always been wonderfully stated but imperfectly implemented and this singular reason has crumbled plans and made education in Nigeria an issue of great concern. Education has been acknowledged as an excellent tool would that bring about advancement and development in the nation as seen in the advanced nations of the world. It leaves one to wonder how come Nigeria, as a nation, has not seen the need to implement her policies in education adequately? From observation, the nation still groups in the dark educationally. This has brought nothing more than distress for the education administrators/managers, planners and other stakeholders. The education planners have their wonderful ideas on paper but gigantic problems are encountered, when it comes to implementing these ideas, (Lenshie, 2023).

Over the years Nigeria has had several educational policies that could not be implemented or were botch at the verge of implementation. For example, the Universal Basic Education programme is one of the educational policies that could not be implemented hitherto. The Universal Basic Education Policy (UBE) which was launched by the Federal Government under the leadership of the former President, Olusegun Obasanjo in September, 1999, actually took-off fully in 2004. The programme become necessary so as to give Nigerians the basic education they need to survive the challenges of the future and become useful citizens to their community, country and indeed around the world (Ekundayo & Akinsuroju, 2019). It is a policy reform of the Federal Government of Nigeria targeted at reforming the basic level of education in Nigeria. According to Federal Ministry of Education (2019), it comprises; 1 year of pre-primary, 6 years of primary and 3 years of junior secondary education.

The scheme is compulsory, free, universal and qualitative for children between the ages of 3 to 14 years. Basic education policy was designed to achieve certain goals and objectives. Universal Basic Education (2014) and Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014) stated the goals of basic education as: to provide the child with diverse basic knowledge and skills for entrepreneurship, wealth generation and educational advancement; to develop patriotic young people equipped to contribute to social development and in the performance of their civic responsibilities; to inculcate values and raise morally upright individuals capable of independent thinking, and who appreciate the dignity of labour; to inspire national consciousness and harmonious co-existence, irrespective of differences in endowment, religion, colour, ethnic and socio-economic background; and to provide opportunities for the child to develop manipulative skills that will enable the child function effectively in the society within the limits of the child's capability.

For the purposes of policy coordination and monitoring of education at the basic level, the Federal Government of Nigeria instituted a Universal Basic Education (UBE) to achieve the following objectives:

- a. Developing in the entire citizenry, a strong conscientiousness for education and a strong commitment to its vigorous promotion;
- b. The provision of compulsory, free, and Universal Basic Education for every Nigerian child of school going age;

- c. Reducing the incidence of drop out from the formal school system, through improved relevance, quality and efficiency;
- d. Catering through appropriate form of complementary approaches to the promotion of basic education, for the learning needs of young persons who for one reason or another have had to interrupt their schooling;
- e. Ensuring the acquisition of appropriate levels of literacy, numeracy, manipulative communicative and life skills as well as the ethical, moral, security and civic values needed for laying a solid foundation for the life-long learning

Be that as it may, Musa and Sa'idu (2019), posited that the targets of universal basic education scheme among other things are; to ensure that 100% of graduates from this scheme possess literacy, numeracy and basic life skills that will enable them to live meaningfully in their societies and at the same time contribute their quotas towards the national development; ensuring that 100% of teachers employed for the programme have minimum teaching qualification of Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE), as well as ensuring that 100% of basic education schools have conducive teaching and learning environment; and lastly, redressing all forms of disadvantages, gender disparity and promotion of inclusive education.

It is important that to state teachers are the drivers of any educational policy, that is they are the vehicles through which the goals of any educational policy are achieved particularly as it pertains to teaching and learning. Thus certain satisfiers are to be put in place to ensure teachers productivity. Amadi and Osazuwa (2019) described productivity as the relationship between output of goods and services and inputs of resources; human and material, used in the production process. Based on this, productivity in the educational system refers to the ratio between the total educational outputs and the resource inputs utilized in the production process. Teachers productivity entails the ability of teachers to bring about high and consistent learning gains in all student taught across all courses or subject areas. The UBE policy has in it certain forces that were aimed at ensuring that teachers productivity is attainable being that the major resource input to the education system is the teaching manpower made up of teachers. The quality and adequacy of these forces are boosters of teacher's productivity and vice versa. They include:

Teachers' professional development: Teachers development entails regular or continuous short in-service training that is aimed at building and sustaining teacher's capacities in the teaching and learning process so they can be more committed and competent. In accordance with Section 9 (b) of the UBE Act, 2004, the Federal Government has approved in 2005 that 70% of the 2% of the Consolidated Revenue Fund (CRF) dedicated for the UBE programme should be expended on three key activities of the UBE programme. These are (1) infrastructural development (70%), (2) textbooks and non – consumable instructional materials (15%) and (3) teacher professional development (15%). Funds for the Teacher Professional Development component must be utilized in the following distribution 60% in the primary 35% in junior secondary and 5% in the pre- primary education levels. Therefore, the UBE does not only recognize the need for professional development of teachers, but it has also earmarked a huge sum of funds for its implementations (Omotayo, 2020).

Teacher development according to Musa and Sa'idu (2019) is an ingredient in enhancing the performance of any school level, while training and development are the processes of behaviour modification of moulding workers in order to integrate the organization needs. Teachers' development programmes such as in-service training programme, workshop programme, in-house training programme, conference programme etc enable teachers to progress from his/her present state of understanding and capability to the future that requires higher level of competency, skills and knowledge. Teachers' development programme is aimed to improve the current level of performance of incumbents in their present job and equip men with potential for higher level responsibilities (Sherma, 2019). As a result of the important roles they play within and outside the school setting, there must be training and re-training of teachers to improve or help them attain the required level of knowledge or skills needed for better performance. For the universal basic education scheme (UBES) to be qualitative enough, Irewole and Akinsuroju (2019) maintained that the Federal Government of Nigeria spelt it out categorically that the minimum teaching qualification that teachers for universal basic education programme must possess is Nigeria Certificate in

Education (NCE). It is disheartening to note that teachers with qualifications lower than the minimum NCE are still found in some states of the federation.

Student-teacher ratio: Student-teacher ratio entails the number of students allotted a teacher in a particular class or subject (Adesoji, et al, 2019). However, Omuemu and Isuku (2019) asserted that student-teacher ratio is also known as class size; small or large. They further stated a class of pupil between 30 and 35 constitutes small or normal class size, while a class of pupil above 35 is considered a large class. In light of the above, class size and student-teacher ratio shall be used interchangeably. The stipulated student-teacher ratio according to the National Policy on Education is 30-35 (FRN, 2014). Sadly, this is not the case in most public schools as there are 40 to 80 pupils in one class, particularly schools in the urban area. The increase in the population of a school affects the size of classes, as such teaching and learning becomes a biting issue. The size of a class that a teacher handles can either facilitate or hamper effective teaching-learning process.

Ezugoh and Ofojebe (2019) found that populated classrooms do not enhance teaching, students learning and performance. This means that there is a tolerable number of students in a classroom that a teacher can manage. When the class size is very large as observable in most of our secondary schools and tertiary institutions, it adversely affects the arrangement of the class which in turn affects classroom management processes that could engender effective teaching and learning. Large classroom presents more challenges for classroom management such as student control, planning, teaching, marking and evaluation. This situation puts teachers under severe pressure. It also creates the opportunity for unserious students to engage in other activities such as discussions unrelated to the topic underway, play games, draw graffiti and minor forms of assault to distract serious students. Conversely, small classes are characterised by lesser strain for teachers as teachers could easily identify specific needs and direct teaching towards meeting them. More so, teachers with small classes could easily have better relationship with each student, understand areas of strength and weaknesses for each of the students, and set targets for them (Adeyemi, 2019).

Facilities: School facilities can be described as both material and non-material resources that facilitate the teaching and learning process in the school. Osuji (2022) defined school facilities as instructional materials, space, equipments structures, machines and accessories within the school which facilitate the teaching and learning activities and at the same time protect the physical well-being of the students. Alimi (2022) viewed school facilities as the space interpretation and physical expression of the school curriculum. The above definitions indicate that school facilities include but not limited to the physical environment of the school, instructional materials, classroom condition, laboratory, library, health care facilities, recreational facilities, cafeteria, furniture, etc. Research shows that the availability of adequate and quality physical facilities in any educational environment is among the determining forces of teachers' productivity (Obonyo, 2019). Facilities in many schools are inadequate and dilapidated, teachers' common are small and lack furniture and other equipment. This makes school hours "unpleasant" for many teachers stay back at school after finishing the subjects that they have for the day.

All of these educational policies as discussed are conspicuous national problems that have taken centre stage in Nigeria's education system. Hence, it is on this premise that this study examined educational policies implementation as a predictor of teachers' productivity in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

Educational policies are aimed at improving the educational system of any society. However, when those policies (i.e. teachers' professional development, student-teacher ratio, provision of school facilities, payment of remuneration and promotion) are not implemented it affects the productivity of teachers, who have the sole responsibility of ensuring that the purpose of the school is achieved. Effective teaching and learning activities are the main purposes for which the school was established; be it primary, secondary or tertiary. It is through effective teaching and learning process that the aims and/or functions of education can be realised. Education as a process of training and instructing individuals, especially young people, through the transmission of skills, values and development of innate capacities, is achieved when the teacher and student interact in order to exchange information. This interaction process is hoped to bring

an all-round development in the individual and by extension the society. It was on this premise that the collapsed Universal Primary Education (UPE) and the ailing Universal Basic Education (UBE) policies came up; the role of education as an instrument for the survival of the individual and the development of society, the promotion of national unity, and the improvement of social and economic features of society was recognised. The policy has suffered several implementation challenges which in turn has impinge on teacher's productivity.

The liberalisation of education which is concomitant with population explosion in our schools has given rise to overcrowding class rooms and inability of proper implementation of educational policies. The situation is not different in Rivers State as teachers handle between 50 to 100 students in a classroom and have to share the same classroom with students due to inadequacy of office spaces. This strains the teacher as he/she must shout in order for the students to hear the instruction, at the end of the day the teacher is completely exhausted. On the other hand, poor remuneration and poor promotion culture has made many teachers to sort for a second job that would cushion the inadequacies of the teaching job, thereby compromising their full attention on the teaching job. The status-quo has truncated the aim of the UBE programme thereby undermining teachers' productivity. The full actualization of the objectives of education can only be feasible when educational policies are fully implemented as teachers' productivity is hinged on the implementation of such policies. From the foregoing the problem of this study was to investigate the educational policies implementation as predictor of teachers' productivity in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. The educational policies in focus include; teachers' professional development, student-teacher ratio and physical facilities.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to investigate the extent educational policies implementation predicts teachers' productivity in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State. The specific objectives of the study sought to:

1. find out the extent to which teachers' development policy implementation predicts teachers' productivity in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. examine the extent to which student-teacher ratio policy implementation predicts teachers' productivity in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State.
3. ascertain the extent to which facilities policy implementation predicts teachers' productivity in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent does teachers' development policy implementation predict teachers' productivity in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. To what extent does student-teacher ratio policy implementation predict teachers' productivity in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State?
3. To what extent does facilities policy implementation predict teachers' productivity in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested under 0.05 level of significance:

1. Teachers' development policy implementation does not significantly predict teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. Student-teacher ratio policy implementation does not significantly predict teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.
3. Facilities policy implementation does not significantly predict teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a correlational research design. Correlational research was adopted to establish the extent the independent variable (Educational Policies Implementation) predict the dependent variable (Teachers’ Productivity). The population of the study comprised 7,492 teachers (i.e. 3,121 male and 4,371 female) of all the 354 public junior secondary schools in Rivers State. Source: Rivers State Universal Basic Education Board, 2024. A sample of 2,247 teachers representing 30% was drawn from the entire population. A stratified sampling technique was adopted to select 6 local government areas spread across 3 Senatorial District (Rivers East, Rivers West, Rivers South-East) in Rivers State where the respondents was selected. The instrument that was used for data collection in this study was a questionnaire of two sets titled: Educational Policies Implementation Questionnaire (EPIQ) and Teachers’ Productivity Questionnaire (TPQ). The instrument has three sections A, B and C. The section A consisted of the demographic information of the respondents, while section B dealt with questionnaire items on Educational Policies Implementation Scale (EPIS) which are made up of five parts. Section C consisted of items on Teachers’ Productivity Questionnaire (TPQ). Both EPIQ and TPQ were structured after the 4-point Likert rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE) = 4 points, High Extent (HE) = 3 points, Low Extent (LE) = 2 points and Very Low Extent (VLE) = 1 point. The instrument was validated and the Cronbach method reliability statistics was used to calculate the reliability coefficients of the instrument, which yielded 0.81 and 0.87 for EPIQ and TPQ. 2,247 copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents, but 2,189 copies were retrieved and were found suitable for data analysis, resulting in 97% retrieval rate. Simple regression was used to answer the research questions, while t-test associated with simple regression was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULT AND ANALYSIS

Research Question 1: *To what extent does teachers’ development policy implementation predict teachers’ productivity in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Simple Regression on the Extent Teachers’ Development Policy Implementation Predict Teachers’ Productivity in Public Junior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Extent of prediction	Decision
1	.574 ^a	.253	.251	25.3%	Low Extent

Decision Rule: 75%- 100% (Very High Extent), 50% - 74% (High Extent), 25%-49% (Low Extent) and 24% - 0% (Very Low Extent)

Table 4.1 revealed that the regression (r) and regression square (r²) coefficients are .574 and .253 respectively, while the adjusted r square is .252. The extent of prediction (i.e. coefficient of determinism) is 25.3% (.253×100). By implication, the result shows that teachers’ development policy implementation predict teachers’ productivity in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State to a low extent by 25.3%.

Research Question 2: *To what extent does student-teacher ratio policy implementation predict teachers’ productivity in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Simple Regression on the Extent Student-Teacher Ratio Policy Implementation Predict Teachers’ Productivity in Public Junior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Extent of Prediction	Decision
1	.311 ^a	.053	.051	5.1%	Very Low Extent

Decision Rule: 75%- 100% (Very High Extent), 50% - 74% (High Extent), 25%-49% (Low Extent) and 24% - 0% (Very Low Extent)

Table 2 revealed that the regression (r) and regression square (r²) coefficients are .311 and .053 respectively, while the adjusted r square is .051. The extent of prediction (i.e. coefficient of determinism) is 5.3% (.053×100). By implication, the result indicates that student-teacher ratio policy implementation

predict teachers' productivity in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State to a very low extent by 5.3%.

Research Question 3: *To what extent does facilities policy implementation predict teachers' productivity in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 3: Simple Regression on the Extent Facilities Policy Implementation Predict Teachers' Productivity in Public Junior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Model	R	r Square	Adjusted r Square	Extent of prediction	Decision
1	.762 ^a	.424	.422	42.4%	Low Extent

Decision Rule: 75%- 100% (Very High Extent), 50% - 74% (High Extent), 25%-49% (Low Extent) and 24% - 0% (Very Low Extent)

Table 3 revealed that the regression (r) and regression square (r²) coefficients are .762 and .424 respectively, while the adjusted r square is .422. The extent of prediction (i.e. coefficient of determinism) is 42.4% (.424×100). By implication, the result reveals facilities policy implementation predict teachers' productivity in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State to a low extent by 42.4%.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Teachers' development policy implementation does not significantly predict teachers' productivity in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: t-test Associated with Simple Regression on the Extent Teachers' Development Policy Implementation Significantly Predict Teachers' Productivity in Public Junior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	p-value	Alpha level	Decision
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
(Constant)	2.325	.133		15.182	.000	0.05	Ho ₁ Accepted
1 Teachers' Development	.147	.041	.371	4.651	.061		

a. Dependent Variable: Teachers' Productivity

Table 4 revealed that standard beta value and t-test are .371 and 4.651. The p-value of 0.061 is higher than the level of significance of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. By implication, teachers' development policy implementation does not significantly predict teachers' productivity in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2: Student-teacher ratio policy implementation does not significantly predict teachers' productivity in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 5: t-test Associated with Simple Regression on the Extent Student-Teacher Ratio Policy Implementation Significantly Predict Teachers' Productivity in Public Junior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	p-value	Alpha level	Decision
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
(Constant)	1.736	.117		14.761	.000	0.05	Ho ₂ Accepted
1 Student-Teacher Ratio	-.072	.033	-.021	-.425	.173		

a. Dependent Variable: Teachers' Productivity

Table 5 revealed that standard beta value and t-test are -.021 and .425. The p-value of .173 is less than the level of significance of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. By implication, student-teacher

ratio policy implementation does not significantly predict teachers' productivity in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 3: Facilities policy implementation does not significantly predict teachers' productivity in secondary schools in secondary schools in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 6: t-test Associated with Simple Regression on the Extent Facilities Policy Implementation Significantly Predict Teachers' Productivity in Secondary Schools in Secondary Schools in Public Junior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	p-value	Alpha level	Decision
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
1	(Constant)	1.721	.295	12.341	.000	0.05	H0 ₃ Rejected
	Facilities	.216	.124	.224	.152		

a. Dependent Variable: Teachers' Productivity

Table 6 revealed that standard beta value and t-test are .224 and .152. The p-value of .041 is less than the level of significance of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. By implication, facilities policy implementation significantly predicts teachers' productivity in secondary schools in secondary schools in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDING

The first finding revealed that teachers' development policy implementation predict teachers' productivity in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State to a low extent by 25.3%. Also, a corresponding finding from test of hypothesis establishes that teachers' development policy implementation does not significantly predict teachers' productivity in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State. These findings are in contradiction with the studies of Yusuf and Fashiku (2016), Thomas and Benjamin (2018), Maifada (2019), Sa'idu (2019), who observed that teacher development policy implementation contributes to teacher productivity. Sa'idu (2019) posited that teacher-development implementation is an ingredient in enhancing the performance of any school level.

However, the findings are in line with Enaohwo (2010) who reported that teachers' development programme is aimed to improve the current level of performance of teachers in their job, but since it is poorly implemented, it has not shown any significant contribution towards teachers' productivity for higher level responsibilities. Jumare (2019) asserted that training and re-training of teachers is expected to increase teachers' productivity thereby increasing students' performance, but in many parts of Nigeria its implementation have been shoddy, thereby predicting insignificant result in teacher productivity in schools. He concluded that one of the means to achieve the mandate of universal basic education policy in Nigeria is through National Capacity Building for UBE teachers, and if properly implemented will yield it desired result.

The second finding of this study revealed that student-teacher ratio policy implementation predict teachers' productivity in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State to a very low extent by 5.3%. Similarly, a corresponding finding from test of hypothesis establishes that student-teacher ratio policy implementation does not significantly predict teachers' productivity in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State. These findings are in agreement with Abiodun-Oyebanji (2012), Ajayi and Adeosun (2017), Boru and Timeria (2018), Molagun (2019), whose empirical works showed that students-teacher ratio policy implementation does not contribute to teacher productivity. According to the scholars, when teachers are faced with large class size or number of students their level of performance reduces due to the fact that they are saddled with several responsibilities of classroom activities.

Also in line with the findings, Boru and Timeria (2019) asserted that large class size adversely affects the arrangement of the class which in turn mitigates classroom management techniques and teacher's productivity. They also added that large class size poses serious challenges for classroom management such as student control, planning, teaching, marking and evaluation. This situation put teachers under

pressure. It also gives room for unserious students to get distracted and engage in activities that hamper effective learning. Some of these activities are discussions unrelated to the topic underway, playing of games, drawing graffiti and engaging in minor forms of assault to distract serious students' poor performance to ineffective teaching and learning birthed by inadequate material and infrastructural resources which are below expectation, with many schools having few classroom accommodation, poor spacing and crowded sets. No wonder Doyle as cited in Pantrock (2020) described large class size as crowded, complex and potentially chaotic environment which does not guarantee teachers' productivity.

The third finding of the study revealed that facilities policy implementation predict teachers' productivity in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State to a low extent by 42.4%. Also, a corresponding finding from test of hypothesis establishes that facilities policy implementation significantly predicts teachers' productivity in secondary schools in secondary schools in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State. These findings corroborate Bullock (2017), PEB Exchange (2018), Lowe (2019), and Bob (2021) whose studies have proven that proper facilities policy implementation predicts teachers' productivity. Bullock (2021) buttressed that when teachers are provided with adequate and conducive facilities in school, it aid them in their job performance. According to the scholar, school administrators must be concerned with the structural and cosmetic conditions of school facilities as they contribute to teachers' productivity. Bullock (2019) in study found that teachers do better in school that were new or renovated recently than in older schools. The overall building condition, the school age of the building, and the windows in the instructional areas were positively related to students performance which is a result of teachers' productivity.

In addition, the findings are in line with Corcoran, et al (2018) who observed that the productivity of teachers in schools in rural areas improved when they are provided with facilities that aid them in their job. The researchers suggested that the working condition of urban teachers should not differ with that of those in rural area so as to enhance their teaching profession. Allan (2019) asserted that teachers who reported working in an unconducive work-environment admitted that it adversely affected their productivity. While poor work environment is a threat to productivity, a supportive and satisfying one is related to higher productivity among teachers.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the study concluded that physical facilities policy implementation significantly predict teachers' productivity in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State, while teachers' development and student-teacher policies implementation do not significantly predict teachers' productivity.

RECOMMENDATION

The following recommendation were made in line with the findings and conclusion of the study:

1. Government should implement teacher development policy by sponsoring teachers for conferences and workshops to enhance their pedagogical skills for improved productivity.
2. Government should recruit more secondary teachers in order to get it right with students-teacher ratio policy so as to improve teachers' productivity.
3. Government through the ministry of education should ensure that teachers are promoted at when due to boost their morale in delivery of their job task.

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